

Prospects and Challenges of Autonomous Merchant Ship: Perspective Bangladesh

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ABSTRACT

Technological innovation in the shipping sector is a constant process, and the introduction of Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) is a significant milestone. The idea of building MASS has already received global interest, especially from the International Maritime Organisation. Bangladesh plays a vital role in international shipping and is one of the leading countries in ship recycling and personnel contributions. As a result, this discussion highlights the difficulties Bangladesh would encounter in implementing the law of the sea's jurisdiction over MASS as a coastline, port, and flag state. Important to this conversation are the International Maritime Organisation's function as a global shipping regulator and the effects of its mandate in resolving these issues. As a state party to UNCLOS, Bangladesh should take these issues into account while implementing new regulations and technology for MASS operations, according to the discussion's conclusion.

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1. Introduction

1.1 Background

An autonomous ship navigates and functions without the need for human intervention by utilising robotics and artificial intelligence. They may be operated remotely from the shore or fully autonomously. Autonomous vessels are equipped with a variety of sensors to provide navigational information, including lidar, radar, Global Positioning System (GPS), infrared and visible spectrum cameras, and Automatic

Identification System (AIS). They come in a variety of shapes and sizes, from small boats to large cargo ships. The Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) regulation is a draft regulation developed by the maritime sector to regulate the operation of autonomous ships.

To determine the optimal course of action, they use artificial intelligence (AI) systems to assess data from these sensors as well as other sources such as traffic and weather. Autonomous ships may be used for several purposes other than monitoring marine ecosystems. Significant

advancements in the field of autonomous vessel technology hold promise for improving global maritime security, the economy, and the environment. Three domains of search and rescue (SAR), marine counter-drug operations, and navigational safety that are of long-term importance to commercial vessels, naval forces, and industry regulators are examined in this article, along with the potential benefits and risks of MASS (Coito J. et al., 2023).

As technology advances, the potential of autonomous ships becomes a reality. Autonomous ships are projected to transform the shipping sector, with benefits ranging from cost savings to increased safety. However, the shift to self-driving ships is not without problems. As one of the largest contributor countries, like Bangladesh, has to convert its systems and train manpower to remain within the world shipping competition. This paper focuses on the prospects of autonomous ships in the context of Bangladesh, and the challenges they will probably face in terms of training, employment, and other navigational aspects and how they can alter the maritime sector.

1.2 Statement of Research Problems

Notwithstanding the possible advantages, autonomous ships will encounter serious risks that compromise their security and functionality. Making ships unmanned would leave crews stranded. The humans who are typically required to properly steer and maintain ships may soon be replaced by digital solutions. Furthermore, upon such replacement, a vessel may be overseen by other machines or by individuals who are unfamiliar with the marine environment, at least initially. So, to meet all the requirements and remain at the front line of the crew contribution country like Bangladesh will have to face various challenges like crew training, legislation and policy implementation, navigational safety and many more. This study

will highlight/ focus on Various prospects of MASS and the challenges that Bangladesh is going to face in the near future.

- a. What are the prospects of MASS operation in Bangladesh?
- b. What are the challenges going to encounter?
- c. What is the probable solution or steps that should take country like Bangladesh?

1.3 Objective of the Study

The main objective of this study is to find out the prospects and challenges for a country like Bangladesh. The specific objectives may be:

- a. To find the perspective of Bangladesh of MASS in terms of safety & security, cost & human error reduction, and economic aspects.
- b. To find the challenges of MASS in terms of legal, job & training, and environmental aspects.

The expected outcome of this study would be an overview of the prospects and challenges of MASS perspective in Bangladesh, which will lead the seafarers to choose the appropriate steps at the right time to remain in the competition of the world maritime industry.

1.4 Significance of the Study

This study has significant implications for policy, performance, research, seafarers' training and knowledge advancement. This study is important for the Government of the People's Republic of Bangladesh (GPRB), the Ministry of Shipping (MOS), the Department of Shipping (DOS), all marine academies, and the Mercantile Marine Office (MMO) to formulate policy guidelines for expanding the Bangladesh flag fleet to compete with other international ship registers and safeguard Bangladesh's maritime interests. This would benefit the whole Bangladeshi marine community.

1.5 Scope of the Study

The context of the study was framed on the perspective and challenges that have an impact on seafarers, policy makers, the shipping community, and other stakeholders working in the shipping industry in Bangladesh.

1.6 Methodology

The study is mainly based on information from various articles, journals, papers and theses related to this topic. Data were used as secondary data from various articles, thesis and articles.

2 Conceptual Discourses

2.1 Various Levels of Autonomous Ship

By classifying MASS as a ship and defining the different levels of autonomy, the IMO aims to systematically address the intricate issues surrounding autonomous shipping and pave the way for a robust regulatory framework that keeps up with the swiftly evolving technological advancements in the maritime industry (Hasan

S.et al., 2023). The degrees of autonomy identified for the scoping exercise are:

Degree one: Ship with automated processes and decision support. Seafarers are on board to operate and control shipboard systems and functions. Some operations may be automated and at times be unsupervised, but with seafarers onboard, ready to take control.

Degree two: Remotely controlled ship with seafarers on board. The ship is controlled and operated from another location. Seafarers are available onboard to take control and operate the shipboard systems and functions.

Degree three: Remotely controlled ship without seafarers on board. The ship is controlled and operated from another location.

Degree four: Fully autonomous ship. The operating system of the ship can make decisions and determine actions by itself.

2.2 Difference Between Conventional Ship Operation and Autonomous Ship Operation

Table 1: Difference Between Conventional Ship Operation and Autonomous Ship Operation

Feature	Conventional Ship Operation	Autonomous Ship Operation
Control	Human crew controls the ship's speed, heading, and position using rudders, propellers, and other systems etc manually	It is operated automatically by using technology. Decisions and actions can be fully automated or involve human operators via remote control centres.
Decision-Making	Decisions are made by the ship's captain and crew on board.	Decisions can partly be made by autonomous systems based on sensor data onboard or by a remotely operated support team from the control station.

Safety	Safety is fully dependent on humans vigilance and actions.	Here, as the system is technology-based, there is less opportunity to commit human error. Safety is dependent on the robustness of the technology and human supervision in remote operations.
Crew	Requires a full, on-board crew for all functions, including navigation and operations.	There might be a smaller number of crew or no crew at all. Mostly controlled by a shore-based remote operation centre handling some or all functions.
Cost	Cost includes crew cost, logistics for crews, and fuel.	This can lower operational costs by reducing crew expenses and potentially improving fuel efficiency, although initial technology investment is high.

Figure 1: Conventional ship operation and autonomous ship operation (Ørnulf Jan Rødseth et al., 2023)

2.3 Review of Existing Literature

There are several research papers on MASS where a number of authors from various countries, as well as Bangladesh, have expressed their thoughts on various points of view. It is mentioned that there are potentialities to improve navigational safety (Burmeister and Rødseth, 2014). It is asserted that most maritime mishaps are caused by "human errors". Thus, substituting the overtired officer of the watch with a nautical officer ashore bears potential to improve the safety of navigation.

Hasan S. et al (2023) discuss the challenges that Bangladesh would face as a coastal port and flag state when enforcing its jurisdiction over MASS under the law of the sea. But the challenges are mostly based on the law of the sea. There are a few more challenges which were not covered.

Autonomous commercial ships are a viable alternative to conventional, human boats with sailors, based on current technology. This approaching change demands the creation of relevant regulations, such as reconsidering outdated training curricula, in connection to a range of areas of the sector, including the future of sailing as a career (K. Bogusławski et al., 2022).

The article by Abudu, R. et al. (2024) looks at important trends and gaps in the application of cybersecurity precautions, autonomous navigation systems, and advanced sensor technologies. Policymakers and industry stakeholders can benefit from the findings, which shed light on the operational issues and technological advancements defining the future of marine safety and security. By tracing the

evolution of technological integration and its effects on maritime operations in a worldwide setting, this work contributes to the scholarly conversation in this field.

Aksari, H. et al. (2021) compared and assessed the viability of Industry 4.0 to examine the impact of self-driving ships on the marine industry. The most important and practical features of self-governing ships have been identified. Additionally, the advantages and consequences of autonomous ships have been demonstrated and explained.

2.4 Example of MASS

According to Bhuiyan et al. (2016) Automation in shipping is a 50-year endeavour. In 1961, the 'Kinkasan Maru' became the first successful automated seagoing ship. The remotely controlled unmanned watercraft were utilised during World War II as gunnery and missile target systems (Corfield and Young, 2006). A surface, underwater, and aerial drone network in communication represents a potentially strong instrument in military surveillance, having been employed since GPS was developed in the early 1980s (Campbell et al., 2012). Unmanned Surface Vehicles (USV) or Autonomous Surface Vehicles (ASV) have been created since 1993, and are mostly employed by oceanographic centres to conduct scientific research at sea.

3. Methodology

This study was completed with a qualitative method where the data were collected from secondary sources. From the various literature, books, journals, etc., the information was

Figure 2: Methodological approach

4. Discussions and Analysis

There are several hurdles to incorporating autonomous ships into the maritime sector, including increases in new building costs due to new designs and technical features, system availability and robustness, cybersecurity and the development of harmonised standards. These issues are not largely due to technological barriers, but rather to the integration of the autonomous ship into the existing maritime operations.

The International Maritime Organisation's (IMO) maritime treaties are critical to preventing accidents at sea because they give a set of principles for safe navigation, although they were created for human navigators. As technology develops in autonomous vehicles and unmanned planes, the law governing air and road travel is under increasing examination. Given intrinsic conservatism and inertia, as well as the basic freedom to travel the oceans, maritime rules are unlikely to alter in the medium term. The creation of regulations for autonomous boats is critical for the deployment of autonomous ships into the maritime realm.

As Bangladesh is contributing a good number of seafarers, the introduction of MASS has direct impact on various matters like cost (in terms of fuel, crew management, technological developments, etc.), technology adaptation, safety & security, reduction of incidents and accidents due to human error, legislation, cybersecurity, job security, piracy, etc. As a country, Bangladesh has to take a few infrastructural developments at the same time, crews need to train for remaining at occupied area. Where there are prospects, the challenges act as a resistance.

4.1 Prospects and Benefits

The application of autonomous vessel technology has the potential to enhance public, environmental and economic situations while also opening up new avenues for digital and personal maritime transportation. Although these issues are still largely unresolved, the International Maritime Organisation (IMO) has carried out a "regulatory scoping exercise" for the use of MASS to address these and other issues related to unmanned and autonomous ships (Coito J. et al., 2023). The IMO will determine whether present IMO instruments may restrict MASS activities, which instruments do not prohibit MASS operations but may require clarification or revision and which instruments are unrelated to MASS operations.

Figure 3: Source: An illustration of the benefits of autonomous ships – from Mitsui O.S.K. Lines, Ltd.

4.1.1 Reduction of Human Errors

We know from history that human mistake has caused several collisions and sea accidents. In a recent occurrence, one of the world's largest cargo ships, the MV Ever Given, became stranded in the Suez Canal in March 2021 owing to high winds. The ship was stuck for six days, impeding traffic from all directions. As a result, the Japanese-owned ship has lost about \$54 billion in revenue (Aksari, H. et al., 2021). Admiral Osama Rabie, Chairman of the Suez Canal Authority, stated, "Suez Canal: Ship blockage may be due to 'human errors' (Aksari, H. et al., 2021). The ship owners of Bangladesh and shipping line owners will enjoy the risk-free shipping business.

4.1.2 Reducing Crew Wedges

According to Aksari, H. et al. (2021), automation has the ability to lessen the reliance on human labour for routine tasks on ships. According to the study in the maritime autonomous systems project findings and technological potentials, Unmanned Navigation utilising Intelligence in Networks anticipated that each autonomous vessel will save more than \$7 million in fuel consumption, crew supplies and salaries over the next 25 years. While cheaper labour lowered labour prices by 60%, another study found that automation might reduce labour costs by 90%. The benefits of autonomous ships include eliminating the expense of crew member salaries and benefits. This is especially important for smaller ships since human expenditures account for a significant share of total expenses (Walker et al., 2019). According to Rolls-Royce, autonomous ships can save more than 20% of overall annual costs (Aksari, H. et al., 2021). Lesser crew wedges will encourage more businessmen to come to this business. It will help to reduce the carrying cost and product cost as well.

4.1.3 Reduction of Fuel Consumption

Autonomous shipping has the ability to considerably raise productivity, cut fuel consumption, and increase time efficiency (Mishra, 2020). According to the research in the maritime autonomous systems project results and technical potentials, MUNIN projected that over 25 years, each autonomous vessel will save over \$7 million in fuel consumption, crew supplies, and compensation. Autonomous ships will very probably increase fuel consumption (Mishra et al., 2020). Massive cargo ships are going autonomous, and the Yara Birkeland is likely to be the first ship to be all-electric and create no emissions. Shipping vehicles account for 3% of worldwide carbon-dioxide emissions; hence, the introduction of zero-emission ships might greatly reduce pollution across the world (Aksari, H. et al., 2021).

4.1.4 Search and Rescue

Coito J. et al. (2023) mentioned that SAR personnel typically confront unique hazards as a result of the situations that need sea rescue. Given these inherent hazards, "the duty to provide assistance at sea is a qualified one." To put it another way, a shipmaster may carry out the rescue without placing the passengers, crew, or ship at risk. The employment of degrees three and four MASS as a SAR force multiplier has the potential to greatly reduce the hazards that individuals experience when conducting maritime SAR operations in the face of large waves, bad weather, and limited visibility. Two possible advantages of MASS are the protection of maritime first responders and the strengthening of SAR operations' resilience, which would otherwise be limited or non-existent.

4.1.5 Reduction of Piracy

Somali pirates cost the East African economy up to \$7 billion in 2010 and \$1.7 billion in 2017 (The State of Maritime Piracy 2018). Pirate incursions on the Sulu and Celebes Seas have forced some merchants to change their routes, which can lead to longer delivery delays (Walker, 2019). West Africa's economy lost \$818.1 million due to piracy in 2017 (The State of Maritime Piracy 2018). It is anticipated that the value of stolen cargo, crew belongings and ship products in Asia would increase from \$4.5 million in 2016 to \$6.3 million. Because autonomous ships won't have human crews to threaten or hold hostages, piracy along some trade routes will be reduced or eliminated. The majority of modern piracy is motivated by the abduction of crew members for financial gain (Aksari, H. et al., 2021).

Figure 4: Reduction of cost year-wise (Source: The economic cost of Somali piracy, as reported by www.oceansbeyondpiracy.org)

4.2 Challenges

The maritime sector has several obstacles when implementing autonomous ships, including shifting building costs due to new designs and technical features, system availability and robustness, cybersecurity, and the creation of standardised standards. These issues are not primarily caused by technological barriers, but by the integration of the autonomous ship into the existing marine operations.

4.2.1 Legal Definition and Status

The concept of "ship" for Maritime Autonomous Surface Ships (MASS) varies depending on maritime rules, making it difficult to define. MASS's legal position is a point of contention, making it difficult to assert jurisdiction over these ships. Because there is no specific legal definition or classification of MASS, coastal states find it difficult to govern and monitor its operations. Coastal countries, such as Bangladesh, will have difficulties in balancing the rights and responsibilities of autonomous vessels in their waters. Recognising MASS as a ship under international law is critical for controlling it in today's marine environment. "Vessel" is defined broadly under the 1972 Convention on International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREG). Although this phrase might include traditional ships. According to the Bangladesh Merchant Shipping Ordinance of 1983, a "ship" is any type of vessel used for navigation that is not rowed, except sailing vessels.

4.2.2 Compliance of UNCLOS

The United Nations Convention on the Law of the Sea (UNCLOS) remains the principal legal framework controlling maritime operations, while its relevance to MASS is contested. Bangladesh and other coastal governments have difficulty understanding UNCLOS regulations about sovereignty over autonomous vessels. The convention does not specifically mention the distinctive qualities of MASS because it was adopted before the widespread usage of autonomous technologies in maritime operations (Hasan S.et al., 2023). The task at hand is to ensure that UNCLOS principles adequately handle jurisdictional problems related to MASS while also ensuring that the

agreement is compatible with the realities of autonomous maritime operations.

Hasan S.et al. (2023) mentioned that Bangladesh, as a coastal and port state, may encounter technological and operational problems in monitoring, inspecting and managing MASS, such as onboard operations. inspection and communication (UNCLOS Article 218). Section 3A of the Territorial Waters and Maritime Zones (Amendments) Act, 2021, recognises underwater vehicles, including remotely controlled underwater vehicles, autonomous underwater vehicles, and unmanned undersea vehicles, in relation to the right of innocent passage in territorial waters. The enforcement of authorities over ships, particularly as a coastal state concerning passage rights (e.g., Articles 17, 21, and 38 of UNCLOS), would change the regulation of MASS.

4.2.3 Collision Avoidance and Navigation

There are challenges in integrating MASS into the existing marine traffic management systems related to navigation and collision avoidance. In contrast to traditional vessels, MASS make decisions exclusively through powerful algorithms and sensors, without the participation of humans (Hasan S.et al., 2023).

4.2.4 Readiness of Docking and Undocking Facilities at Bangladesh Ports

All the ports of Bangladesh operate the docking and undocking in a traditional way with the assistance of tug, pilot, and mooring crews, with the assistance of visual assessment and communication. On the other hand, the autonomous ship is assisted by AI based docking system, Light Detection and Ranging (LIDAR) and autonomous tug assistance. Bangladesh ports are far away from this advanced technology in terms of training and infrastructure.

Figure 5: Docking and Undocking procedure of a conventional ship and MASS

4.2.5 Readiness of Bangladesh in Terms of Maintenance

The conventional ship needs regular maintenance to keep the ship operational, but the MASS ships' onboard ship maintenance is minimal, and shore based technical or repair team will work when in dock. At present, Bangladesh lacks sufficient trained technical personnel in robotics, AI diagnosis and digital maintenance centres. Bangladesh is still not ready to handle the MASS ship maintenance in terms of spare time and spare parts. At present, Bangladesh is taking support from foreign countries by importing a major part of the spare parts, especially from China.

4.2.6 Lack of Legal and Regulatory Manpower

At present Department of Shipping (DoS) needs to develop experts on both maritime law and autonomy technology. At present, the DoS primarily deals with conventional ship safety inspections and certification under SOLAS and IMO standards. For this, they need to train legal and technical experts.

4.2.7 Shore Control Station and Expert Operators

Generally, a shore control station equipped with modern equipment, communication, radar and other monitoring systems, which are not available in Bangladesh. Bangladesh needs to build infrastructure and skilled and trained people to operate the shore control station. The traffic system is still manual, and also the traffic sign/ signal.

4.2.8 Mariners Knowledge and Technological Integration

Bangladesh Marine Academies are not designed to train on an autonomous ship. The curricula are still for conventional ships. The navigation, control system, safety guides and overall

training system are yet to start for growing competence for the autonomous curriculum. How the operators will act and the safety measures will be determined by Bangladesh. These preparations should start now.

4.2.9 International Safety Standard

The lack of specific international regulations or legislation tailored to MASS's unique characteristics is a significant impediment to asserting jurisdiction over these ships. There is a vacuum that has to be addressed immediately since the rapid growth of maritime technology has exceeded the construction of necessary international regulatory frameworks (Hasan S. et al., 2023).

Bangladesh is yet to step up to the formal education and infrastructural development in terms of COLREG (The Convention on the International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea, 1972). Bangladesh and other coastal governments struggle to bring their national laws into compliance with changing international standards; this is a process that calls for constant communication and collaboration. This is a process that requires immediate attention because the rapid advancement of marine technology has outpaced the development of relevant international regulatory frameworks.

4.2.10 Cyber Security Concerns

The need to update or add to the current laws is supported by a number of factors, including the rapidly evolving nature of autonomous technologies, the unique privacy and data security issues raised by MASS and the worldwide movement to create specialised laws for autonomous systems. Bangladesh and other coastal nations have the problem of developing effective cybersecurity rules to protect against external meddling, unauthorised access and data leaks. Because Bangladesh lacks a defined data

protection legislation, there may be a gap in addressing MASS privacy concerns. Even while present standards cover certain areas of digital security, they may not provide a comprehensive framework for securing private data and ensuring ethical data management in autonomous maritime systems.

4.2.11 Job Factors and Human Replacement Threats

“Training will change more rapidly, as technology seems to be in advance of the competency training of the mariners onboard. I think there’s a gap there that needs to be bridged and crew to be ahead of that particular curve”

- Capt. John Dolan, Deputy Director, Loss Prevention, Standard Club

There might be a thought that the seafarers may lose their job because lack of technological adaptation of MASS. If the seafarers are unable to take the appropriate training or course which is required for MASS operation, then there is a possibility of remaining jobless. Certainly, these

ships still require human controls to function. The employees and mariners just need to receive coaching and acquire expertise in this field (Johns et al., 2018). Furthermore, the advent of any technology may displace certain occupations at the same time.

The Hamburg School of Business Administration (HSBA) researched the probable effects of autonomous ships on the activities of the seamen and the international shipping industry, and the research found that there would be no shortage of jobs for seafarers, particularly officers, in the next few decades (Johns et al., 2018). However, the size of crews may decrease owing to technological advancements on board, but there may also be significant extra occupations ashore that require nautical knowledge. Additionally, the report evaluates the benefits and hazards of digitisation in global supply chains and ship automation operations (Askari, H. et al., 2021).

Figure 6: A report on Autonomous Ship on March 22 (Executive Consultancy)

Figure 7: A report on the Autonomous Ship on March 22 (Executive Consultancy)

Rapid integration of autonomous technologies into marine operations is a noteworthy trend in the market for autonomous ships. Advances in artificial intelligence, machine learning, sensors, and communication systems are driving this trend by making it possible to create highly advanced autonomous ships that can carry out a variety of nautical activities with little assistance from humans. The desire for increased safety, operational efficacy, and cost-effectiveness in maritime transportation is the main force behind this movement. North America, Europe, and the Asia-Pacific area hold the largest proportion. 60% of the market is in North America. Following that, the rest of the world accounts for 40% of the worldwide market.

4.2.12 Environmental Concern

According to the **International Convention for the Prevention of Pollution from Ships (MARPOL)**, MASS confronts a variety of challenges while attempting to comply with

norms designed for conventional ships. Waste management, pollution control and energy efficiency are some of the problems. MASS has challenges in assessing responsibility and handling mishaps under MARPOL. Coordination and standardisation of MARPOL compliance for MASS among nations must be carefully examined because of the international nature of maritime traffic. Global regulatory harmonisation is required to develop a cohesive and effective framework for the autonomous marine industry. MASS, the international nature of marine traffic needs global coordination for MARPOL compliance, and the rising dependence on automation and digital systems raises cybersecurity concerns that must be addressed in order to prevent environmental pollution (Hasan S.et al., 2023).

Figure 8: Conceptual diagrams of prospects and challenges of MASS

4.3 Steps to Overcome the Challenges

a. Steps need to be taken in line with IMO, International Regulations for Preventing Collisions at Sea (COLREG) and other related conventions to revise the Bangladesh Merchant Shipping Ordinance of 1983.

b. Necessarily amendment has to be done Territorial Waters and Maritime Zones (Amendments) Act, 2021(Sec 3A), considering UNCLOS and other related autonomous laws. Policymakers may want to consider developing new legislation or amending existing laws in order to create a strong legal framework that addresses the complexities of MASS

while striking a balance between innovation and the protection of individual rights, environmental concerns, and international collaboration.

c. Bangladesh and other coastal nations must adjust present maritime rules to fit MASS's unique navigational demands. This includes dealing with issues such as autonomous vessel right of way, communication protocols and emergency procedures.

d. Thus, to meet International Safety Standard problem, worldwide cooperation is needed to create and execute international standards that consider the special characteristics of autonomous vessels.

e. To ensure the safe sailing of autonomous ships on shared waters, precise criteria for vessel-to-vessel interactions must be developed. Advanced collision avoidance technologies must be included.

f. Effective cybersecurity measures must be designed and implemented utilising a multidimensional approach that includes international collaboration, regulatory frameworks, and technological solutions. The challenge is in adapting legal frameworks to address the dynamic nature of cybersecurity issues of mass fatalities and staying abreast of evolving cyberthreats.

g. Skill development by arranging various training program both governmental and non-governmental, may help to keep pace with others. Curriculum may be taken for both new seafarers and those who are serving on conventional ships.

5. Conclusion

The age of autonomy on the world's waters has arrived. As the preceding discussion has sought to explain, this fact holds the possibility of a more competent worldwide regime for MASS operations. There are enormous advantages to this revolutionary system, and it will change the shipping industry in many areas, such as the reduction of crew costs, fuel savings, elimination of human errors, and cost-effective operation. An autonomous vehicle should operate safely and effectively in a real-world environment while performing operations of direct commercial value, which can be manufactured, maintained, deployed, operated and retrieved at an acceptable cost (Rodseth, 2015).

Nevertheless, there are many challenges, such as social, economic and regulatory ones while implementing this autonomous system. It has been emphasised that each of these potentials has significant hurdles and risks. Specifically, the specific boundaries of the responsibility to offer help at sea, traditionally discharged by a vessel's master, have yet to be determined in the context of MASS operations. Finally, autonomous vessel technology may one day make ocean navigation safer by lowering or eliminating human error, but that day has not yet arrived. Furthermore, much of the existing navigational safety system incorporated in international documents, such as the COLREGS and SOLAS Conventions, assumes human crews and, at times, requires distinctly human judgments. Finally, while autonomous vessel technologies may one day render ocean navigation a safer enterprise by reducing or removing human error, that day has not yet come. However, fully resolving these concerns will need the same technical, legal, and diplomatic inventiveness and commitment that has taken us to the brink of an autonomous future at sea.

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Conflict of interest

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